

Investigation on Structural, Transport, Magnetic and Magnetocaloric properties of Cu substitution in CoMnGe alloys

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Abstract

We investigate structure, transport, magnetic and magnetocaloric effect in $MnCo_{1-x}Cu_xGe$ ($x = 0, 0.3, 0.7$) intermetallic alloys. The non-magnetic (Cu) element is positioned at Co site, which results drastic change in the crystallographic structure (Orthorhombic-Hexagonal) and exhibits metal-insulator behavior. The magneto-structural transition reduces and changes from First (AFM-FM) to Second (FM-PM) order with Cu substitution. Giant MCE is observed near RT (307 K) for parent sample and decreases towards lower temperatures for Cu doped samples. The change in magnetic entropy (ΔS_M) decreases with increasing Cu substitution. Refrigeration capacities (RC) linearly increase with magnetic field for all samples and decreases with Cu doping. The order of transition is confirmed for $x=0.2, 0.4, 0.6$ alloys by the analysis of critical exponents via modified Arrott plots and the Kouvel Fisher method. The calculation of Landau coefficients, Spontaneous magnetizations and local exponent from isothermal curves will be discussed in details manner.

Keywords: MnCoGe, Metal-Insulator, Magnetic refrigeration, Critical exponents.

References:

1. N T Trung *et al*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **96** (2010) 172504.
2. Xiaodong Si *et al*, *Solid state communications.* **247** (2016) 27.
3. P Shamba *et al*, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter.* **25** (2013) 056001.
4. Tapas Samanta *et al*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **101** (2012) 242405.

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